

On the Accuracy-Energy Tradeoff for Hierarchical Federated Learning via Satisfaction Equilibrium

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Abstract—Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) has recently emerged as a promising method to overcome the limitations of conventional Federated Learning (FL) in terms of communication inability of the end users with the cloud and increased backhaul network traffic when considering implementations over wireless networks. Nevertheless, to reap the benefits of HFL, proper user association with the different edge servers and wireless resource allocation is required. Unlike existing works - that in their majority treat unilaterally a single objective using centralized optimization techniques - in this paper, we particularly aim to explore the tradeoff induced between the users' local model training accuracy and personal energy consumption in a distributed manner. The joint problem of user-to-edge-server association and uplink power allocation for transmitting the users' local model parameters to the edge is formulated and solved as a game in satisfaction form. Each user autonomously seeks to achieve a target accuracy-energy ratio by selecting their edge association and uplink transmission power level, while their cumulative decisions result in a desired Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE) point. Specifically, to determine the respective SE of the formulated game, a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm is utilized. Numerical results obtained via modeling and simulation demonstrate the operational and performance characteristics of the proposed framework in terms of achieving the users' personally desired tradeoff value.

Index Terms—Hierarchical Federated Learning, Game Theory, Satisfaction Equilibrium, User Association, Power Allocation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The remarkable surge of the Internet of Things (IoT) and social networking applications resulted in an unprecedented increase in the amount of data generated on users' devices daily. The necessity of using all this data by various contemporary Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, and aggregating them by centralized computing entities, i.e., cloud servers, raises serious privacy and communication concerns [1]. Federated Learning (FL) method has recently received much attention, pushing users to exchange model parameters with the servers rather than raw data. However, direct communication with the cloud can cause an increased backhaul network traffic, while some users can face connectivity issues due to the wireless environment's limitations (e.g., obstacles). To deal with these issues, a variation of the FL model, the Hierarchical Federated Learning (HFL) method, has been proposed [2].

Based on the HFL method, the global model is produced in a distributed manner by locally training models at the end-user devices using their data and then aggregating their model parameters in the servers. To reduce the communication cost of traditional FL, HFL suggests adding an extra layer of edge model aggregation where several edge servers facilitate the aggregation and transmission of users' model parameters to the cloud. The users are associated with different edge servers and more efficient user-edge updates can be performed, resulting in a significant reduction in both the convergence time and the consumed energy [2]. Nevertheless, considering a wireless HFL network, the imbalanced user distribution and Radio Access Network's (RAN) traffic may prove to be an impediment, affecting training model accuracy and users' energy consumption.

In this paper, our goal is to address this type of challenge in a wireless HFL network consisting of two model aggregation layers, i.e., edge and cloud. Each user in the network contributes to creating the global learning model, though having a different personal target regarding its local model's accuracy versus energy consumption tradeoff. A framework for the joint problem of user-to-edge-server association and resource allocation in terms of the power used to transmit the users' model parameters in the uplink is designed, aiming to strike a balance between each user's local model's accuracy and energy consumption. The joint problem is modeled as a game in satisfaction form [3] and the Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE), at which the users' personal targeted accuracy-energy ratio is satisfied, is derived.

A. Related Work & Motivation

The HFL method is currently an active area of research owing to its potential to address several challenges in traditional FL, such as communication overhead, data privacy, and heterogeneity of devices. In [2], a user-edge-cloud HFL system is compared to single-layer cloud-based and edge-based FL, and it is shown that the model training time and the users' energy consumption can be reduced. Respectively, the authors in [4], propose a variation of the FL method, in which the users are arranged into multiple clusters based on their computing capacity and transmission rate, and hierarchical aggregation is performed. It is proved that the latter method reduces both the training latency and the network traffic. In [5], a multi-layer FL architecture is presented to allow the model aggregation

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at different layers, achieving a decreased energy consumption without affecting to a great extent the model accuracy.

As a result of the attractive features of HFL, several studies are focused on the proper configuration of the training model parameters and network resource allocation to improve even more its performance. In [1], the joint problem of user association and bandwidth allocation in the access network part between the users and the edge is solved via conventional optimization techniques, targeting the minimization of the learning latency and total data distribution distance under the non-Independent Identically Distributed (non-IID) case. A similar user association and resource allocation problem is treated in [6] - though in a distributed manner - based on Stackelberg and evolutionary game formulations. A Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based scheme for the users' association to the edge, their uplink transmission and local computing power allocation is proposed in [7], to simultaneously minimize the training latency, model accuracy, and users' energy consumption. However, although there exist a handful of works that study the joint optimization of the FL model and wireless network parameters, much focus is not given to achieving a good tradeoff between these metrics.

In detail, the users participating in an HFL process aim to obtain good accuracy for the model produced without necessarily consuming large amounts of energy, which will probably maximize their utility but concurrently will reduce their (or the network's) limited resources. For this purpose, games in satisfaction form [3] comprise an effective alternative to normal-form games when considering distributed solution concepts based on Game Theory. The main difference between these games is that the competing players do not target to maximize a desired metric but to satisfy their minimum Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. Games in satisfaction form find a wide range of applications in networking. For example, in [8], a game in satisfaction form is formulated to deal with the problem of user association in heterogeneous networks to guarantee a good tradeoff between the profits and the costs of the users. Also, in [9], a distributed classification scenario where users provide data to an edge server to train a classifier, is modeled as a game in satisfaction form, and an appropriate algorithm is proposed to determine the SE.

B. Contributions & Outline

Following the discussion above, different objectives during the user association and resource allocation procedure can lead to contradicting outcomes concerning the achieved local model accuracy and users' energy consumption. A user-to-edge-server association steered by balancing users' data across the different edge servers to force an IID data case may result in increased wireless communication energy consumption. Inversely, an association mechanism purely based on favorable wireless communication conditions may yield poor learning model accuracy. Achieving an accuracy-energy tradeoff becomes even more complex when accounting for the concurrent allocation of radio resources in the RAN part. In this context, the main contributions of this work are summarized as follows.

- 1) A wireless HFL network is considered and the users' achieved tradeoff between local model accuracy and personal energy consumption due to communication and computing functions is modeled. Specifically, the information entropy is used to estimate each user's local model accuracy based on the total data distribution of all users to the different edge servers.
- 2) The joint user-to-edge-server association and uplink transmission power allocation is formulated as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form, based on which each user autonomously determines an efficient solution that satisfies its minimum targeted accuracy-energy ratio.
- 3) A Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm is utilized to derive the joint problem's Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE) in a distributed manner. Detailed numerical results demonstrate the operation and effectiveness of the proposed framework toward achieving the targeted tradeoff.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model. In Section III the model of the HFL method adopted is analyzed. In Section IV, the joint user-to-edge-server and uplink power allocation problem is formulated as a game in satisfaction form, and the corresponding SE is defined and derived via the introduced RL algorithm. Section V regards the framework's performance evaluation, and Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a wireless HFL network, consisting of a set of users $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n, \dots, N\}$, a set of edge servers $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, m, \dots, M\}$, and a cloud server, aiming to train a global learning model collaboratively. The edge servers are hosted and collocated with the RAN's base stations. Assuming that all users $n \in \mathcal{N}$ lie within the serving area of all base stations and thus of all edge servers, each user autonomously selects to associate with one of the available edge servers to transmit its model parameters. The set of users associated with server m is denoted as $\mathcal{N}_m = \{1, \dots, n, \dots, N_m\}$. To indicate the association between a user n and an edge server m , we define a binary variable $a_{n,m} \in \{0, 1\}$. If $a_{n,m} = 1$, user n is connected to edge server m , and conversely. Each edge server m aggregates its associated users' local models and creates an edge model. Subsequently, the edge models are collected and aggregated by the cloud server to form the global model.

Each user n has a local dataset $\mathcal{D}_n = \{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^{D_n}$ of cardinality D_n , where \mathbf{x}_j is the j -th input sample and y_j is the corresponding class. The different classes of the dataset are denoted by the set $\mathcal{C} = \{1, \dots, c, \dots, C\}$. The data volume stemming from the different users $n \in \mathcal{N}_m$ associated with edge server m is indicated by $\mathcal{D}_m = \bigcup_{n=1}^{N_m} \mathcal{D}_n = \{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^{D_m}$, while the total dataset of the network is defined as $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup_{n=1}^N \mathcal{D}_n = \{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^D$.

A. Communication Model

The network is using a total bandwidth of B [Hz] for the wireless access, which is equally divided and allocated to the different base stations and their edge servers. Therefore, the

available bandwidth for communication between a server m and its corresponding users $n \in N_m$ is equal to $B_m = \frac{B}{M}$ [Hz]. The different users' $n \in \mathcal{N}_m$ local model transmissions to server m are multiplexed in the power domain, using the Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) technique. We define as $G_{n,m}$ the channel gain between user $n \in N_m$ and edge server m and as $p_{n,m}$ [W] the corresponding uplink transmission power level.

Without loss of generality, we assume that the channel gains between users $n \in N_m$ and edge server m are sorted in ascending order, such as $G_{1,m} \leq \dots \leq G_{n,m} \leq \dots \leq G_{N_m,m}$. The decoding of the users' signals at the edge server's m receiver starts from the highest channel gain user and is implemented by employing the Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) technique. Thus, the achieved data rate of user $n \in N_m$ in the uplink is:

$$R_{n,m} = B_m \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_{n,m} G_{n,m}}{\sum_{n'=1}^{n-1} G_{n',m} p_{n',m} + I_0^m} \right) [\text{bps}]. \quad (1)$$

It should be noted that this work proposes a user-centric framework for the joint user association and power allocation problem, and, thus, the communications performed at the backhaul part of the network between the edge servers and the cloud are not studied. It can be assumed that there exists a wired connection between the edge servers and the cloud, while the extension of this framework to integrated wireless access and backhaul networks is part of our future work.

B. Energy Consumption Model

During the learning process, each user consumes a certain amount of energy, contributing to the successful production of the global model. This energy consumption is a result of two components. The first one is related to the local computation executed by each user to train its local model. The users $n \in N$ computing energy consumption is given by [2]:

$$E_n^{\text{cmp}} = \sum_{i=1}^{c_n D_n} \frac{a_n}{2} f_n^2 = \frac{a_n}{2} c_n D_n f_n^2 \quad [J], \quad (2)$$

where $a_n/2$ is the effective capacitance coefficient of the user's n chipset, c_n is the number of Central Processing Unit (CPU) cycles required to execute a sample of data, and f_n [CPU cycles/sec] is the CPU frequency of user's n device.

The second component refers to the transmission of each user's n model parameters to the associated edge server m for edge model aggregation. The transmission energy consumption of user $n \in N_m$ is given by [2]:

$$E_{n,m}^{\text{tx}} = \frac{Z(\mathbf{w}_n) p_{n,m}}{R_{n,m}} \quad [J], \quad (3)$$

where $Z(\mathbf{w}_n)$ is the data size in bits of the local model parameters' vector \mathbf{w}_n , i.e., the weights, transmitted to update the edge model.

III. HIERARCHICAL FEDERATED LEARNING MODEL

In this section, the HFL method adopted for global model training is summarized. In particular, the considered HFL method comprises the following three sequential and iterative stages:

- 1) *Local Model Training and Update*: At the first HFL stage, each user n initially acquires the aggregated model from the associated edge server. Based on that, a new local model is being trained, using the local dataset \mathcal{D}_n . The local model update of each user is repeated for a number of κ_1 iterations before continuing to the next stage. Let i denote the local model update iteration at the user device. Then the local model update at user n is:

$$\mathbf{w}_n^i = \mathbf{w}_n^{i-1} - \eta \nabla F_n(\mathcal{D}_n, \mathbf{w}_n^{i-1}), \quad (4)$$

where η is the learning rate of the training, and F_n is the empirical loss function, the minimization of which is targeted by the training process. The latter function is defined as:

$$F_n(\mathcal{D}_n, \mathbf{w}_n) = \frac{1}{D_n} \sum_{i=1}^{D_n} f(\mathbf{x}_j, y_j, \mathbf{w}_n), \quad (5)$$

where f is the empirical loss function of the j -th data sample, capturing the classification error of the model for the j -th data sample. In our classification model training, we adopt the cross-entropy loss function [10].

- 2) *Edge Model Aggregation*: After κ_1 iterations of the users' local model updates, each user n transmits the updated local parameters \mathbf{w}_n to its associated edge server m . Subsequently, each edge server m collects the weights from the users $n \in \mathcal{N}_m$ and performs the aggregation to derive an updated edge model \mathbf{w}_m^i . In this work, we adopt the FedAvg algorithm for edge model aggregation [11]. The updated edge model at edge server m is derived as follows:

$$\mathbf{w}_m^i = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_m} D_n \mathbf{w}_n^i}{D_m}, \quad \text{if } i \bmod \kappa_1 = 0. \quad (6)$$

Immediately after the aggregation, the local model \mathbf{w}_n^i , $\forall n \in N_m$ is updated and replaced by \mathbf{w}_m^i . This procedure is also repeated for a number of κ_2 iterations before the third stage takes place.

- 3) *Cloud Model Aggregation*: The last step of the HFL method concerns the aggregation of the edge servers' models by the cloud. After κ_2 edge model aggregations, i.e., $\kappa_1 \kappa_2$ local model updates of the users, each edge server m uploads its updated parameters \mathbf{w}_m^i to the cloud. Similar to the edge model aggregation, we adopt the FedAvg algorithm for the cloud model aggregation. The aggregated cloud parameters are calculated as:

$$\mathbf{w}^i = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M D_m \mathbf{w}_m^i}{D}, \quad \text{if } i \bmod \kappa_1 \kappa_2 = 0. \quad (7)$$

The model produced by the cloud is the global model that is transmitted back to the users to facilitate the next training iteration.

The three stages of the HFL method are repeated for K iterations to achieve the desired accuracy for the global model. In summary, the stages of HFL are presented in Algorithm 1 [2].

Algorithm 1 Hierarchical Federated Learning Algorithm

```

1: Initialize all users parameters  $\mathbf{w}_n^0$ ;
2: for  $i = 1 : K$  do
3:   for each user  $n \in \mathcal{N}$  in parallel do
4:     Update local model according to (4);
5:   end for
6:   if  $i \bmod \kappa_1 = 0$  then
7:     for each edge server  $m \in \mathcal{M}$  in parallel do
8:       Aggregate edge model according to (6);
9:       if  $i \bmod \kappa_1 \kappa_2 \neq 0$  then
10:        for each user  $n \in \mathcal{N}_m$  in parallel do
11:          Update  $\mathbf{w}_n^i = \mathbf{w}_m^i$ ;
12:        end for
13:       end if
14:     end for
15:   end if
16:   if  $i \bmod \kappa_1 \kappa_2 = 0$  then
17:     Aggregate global model according to (7);
18:     for each user  $n \in \mathcal{N}$  in parallel do
19:       Update  $\mathbf{w}_n^i = \mathbf{w}^i$ ;
20:     end for
21:   end if
22: end for

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IV. JOINT USER ASSOCIATION & RESOURCE ALLOCATION BASED ON SATISFACTION EQUILIBRIUM

In this section, we study the joint problem of user association with the edge servers and uplink power allocation for transmitting the users' local model parameters to the edge servers. The joint problem is formulated as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form, and Satisfaction Equilibria (SE) that satisfy the accuracy and energy requirements of the users are examined. A Reinforcement-Learning (RL)-based algorithm is also presented to obtain the different SEs.

A. Problem Formulation

As discussed earlier, the association of users to the available edge servers and the resource allocation in the network can affect both the learning performance and the energy cost of the HFL. An inconvenient association of users to the available edge servers can cause an imbalanced distribution in terms of both data to the different edge servers and traffic load to the RAN, decreasing the accuracy of the global model and increasing users' energy consumption. In this work, we aim to achieve a target tradeoff between the training accuracy of the global model produced by the HFL method and energy consumption on the users' side. To this end, we seek to optimize the user association $a_{n,m} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$ and their uplink transmission power $p_{n,m}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}$ to the associated edge server.

In more detail, each user is characterized by a utility function u_n that captures the tradeoff between the two quantities under consideration while seeking to reach a particular threshold u_n^{thr} to maintain the accuracy-energy tradeoff up to its personally desired level. Each user's n utility function is defined as:

$$u_n = \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} \frac{H(\mathcal{D}_m)}{E_{n,m}^{tx} + \kappa_1 E_n^{cmp}}. \quad (8)$$

The numerator of (8) represents the users' data distribution among the edge servers, which is expressed by the information entropy $H(\mathcal{D}_m)$ metric. The highest the total entropy of the network is, the closer the network is to the IID case, i.e., the edge servers possess samples of all the different classes included in the dataset \mathcal{D} . The entropy of each edge server's m data volume \mathcal{D}_m is calculated as [12]:

$$H_m(\mathcal{D}_m) = - \sum_{c=1}^C P_m^c(\mathcal{D}_m) \cdot \log(P_m^c(\mathcal{D}_m)), \quad (9)$$

where $P_m^c(\mathcal{D}_m)$ is the proportion of samples of class c in \mathcal{D}_m . Accordingly, the total entropy of the network is defined as:

$$H(\mathcal{D}_m) = \sum_{m=1}^M H_m(\mathcal{D}_m). \quad (10)$$

Continuing with the definition of users' utility function, the denominator of (8) represents the total energy consumption of users during an edge iteration, i.e., k_1 local model iterations.

B. Satisfaction Game Formulation & Equilibrium

The interactions between the users regarding the joint association and power allocation are formulated as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form that is described by the tuple $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \{\mathcal{S}_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}, \{f_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}})$. In this tuple, \mathcal{N} is the set of players, i.e., users, and $\mathcal{S}_n = \{(p_{n,m}, x_n) | p_{n,m} \in (0, p_{max}], x_n \in \mathcal{M}\}$ is each user's $n \in \mathcal{N}$ action space of cardinality S_n , where $s_n \triangleq (p_{n,m}, x_n)$ is every feasible combination of power level and edge server selection, and p_{max} [W] is the maximum feasible power level. It should be noted that the parameter x_n determines the edge server $m \in \mathcal{M}$ with which user n is associated, and based on which the association parameters $a_{n,m}$ are concluded. The set f_n includes the actions of user n from set \mathcal{S}_n that satisfy the minimum utility requirements given the actions already selected by the rest of the users. This set is defined as:

$$f_n(\mathbf{s}_{-n}) = \{s_n \in \mathcal{S}_n | u_n(s_n, \mathbf{s}_{-n}) \geq u_n^{thr}\}, \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{s}_{-n} denotes the actions of all users $n \in \mathcal{N}$ except for user n .

The outcome of a game in satisfaction form is called Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE), the formal definition of which is provided in the following.

Definition 1 (Satisfaction Equilibrium). An action profile $\mathbf{s}^* = (s_1^*, \dots, s_n^*, \dots, s_N^*)$ is a Satisfaction Equilibrium for game \mathcal{G} if:

$$s_n^* \in f_n(\mathbf{s}_{-n}^*), \forall n \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (12)$$

C. Learning Satisfaction Equilibrium

To determine any SE of the game \mathcal{G} , an RL algorithm is introduced [3]. This algorithm is executed in a fully distributed manner, and we assume that users know all their possible actions and the latest selected actions by others. Moreover, the users can observe their achieved utility to check whether the threshold requirement is satisfied. For the convenience of analysis, we index the elements of each user's n action set S_n with the index $l_n \in \mathcal{L}_n = \{1, \dots, S_n\}$, in any desired sequence. Accordingly, the l_n -th action of user n is denoted as s_{n,l_n} .

The proposed algorithm is executed in iterations τ . Each user n is characterized by a probability distribution $\pi_n(\tau) = (\pi_{n,1}(\tau), \dots, \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau), \dots, \pi_{n,S_n}(\tau))$ that indicates its preference towards a specific action s_{n,l_n} at iteration τ and based on which the action at the next iteration $\tau + 1$ is selected. At the first iteration ($\tau = 0$), a uniform distribution is being used, i.e., $\pi_{n,l_n}(0) = \frac{1}{S_n}, \forall s_{n,l_n} \in \mathcal{S}_n$, meaning that all feasible actions from the set \mathcal{S}_n have equal probability to be selected. At the rest of the iterations ($\tau > 0$), the users probabilistically select an action, calculate their utility, and check whether this action satisfies their predefined threshold u_n^{thr} . Based on that, the probability distribution remains unchanged in case the constraint is satisfied; otherwise, it is updated as follows before the next algorithm iteration takes place:

$$\pi_{n,l_n}(\tau + 1) = \begin{cases} \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau), & \text{if } u_n(\tau) \geq u_n^{thr}, \\ g(\pi_{n,l_n}(\tau)), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$g(\pi_{n,l_n}(\tau)) = \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau) + \lambda_\tau r_{n,\tau} (\mathbb{1}_{\{s_n(\tau)=s_{n,l_n}\}} - \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau)). \quad (14)$$

In this rule, i.e., Eq. (14), $s_n(\tau)$ is the action selected by user n at iteration τ , and λ_τ is the learning rate of the algorithm. Furthermore, $r_{n,\tau}$ is the reward function of the RL process which is defined as:

$$r_{n,\tau} = \frac{u_n^{max} - u_n(\tau) - u_n^{thr}}{2u_n^{max}}, \quad (15)$$

where u_n^{max} is the maximum utility of user n and $u_n(\tau)$ is the utility of user n at iteration τ . Specifically, the term maximum utility u_n^{max} of user n indicates the utility value achieved when user n is the only user associated with its closest from a geographical point of view server, experiencing the lowest possible interference from the rest of the users, while the rest of the users are associated to the remaining edge servers in a way that maximum possible entropy is achieved. Overall, the rule in Eq. (14) used for the probability distribution update aims to assign higher probabilities to actions that increase the utility value, and thus they can satisfy the constraint of u_n^{thr} .

The RL algorithm for determining the non-cooperative game's \mathcal{G} SE is presented in Algorithm 2. It is worth mentioning that the selection of the initial actions can affect the convergence of the algorithm. To avoid running into infinite loops, the algorithm is terminated after a maximum number of iterations τ_{max} in case the system has not already converged to an SE.

Algorithm 2 Satisfaction Equilibrium RL Algorithm

- 1: Initialize $\tau = 0$;
 - 2: **for** each $n \in \mathcal{N}$ in parallel **do**
 - 3: **for** each $s_{n,l_n} \in \mathcal{S}_n$ **do**
 - 4: $\pi_{n,l_n}(0) = \frac{1}{S_n}$;
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: Select an action $a_n(0) \sim \pi_n(0)$;
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **while** $\exists n \in \mathcal{N}, u_n(\tau) < u_n^{thr}$ **do**
 - 9: **for** each $n \in \mathcal{N}$ in parallel **do**
 - 10: Update distribution $\pi_n(\tau + 1)$ according to (13);
 - 11: **if** $u_n(\tau) \geq u_n^{thr}$ **then**
 - 12: $s_n(\tau + 1) = s_n(\tau)$;
 - 13: **else**
 - 14: $s_n(\tau + 1) \sim \pi_n(\tau + 1)$;
 - 15: **end if**
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: Update $\tau = \tau + 1$;
 - 18: **end while**
-

V. EVALUATION & RESULTS

In this section, we perform a numerical evaluation of the proposed framework via modeling and simulation to demonstrate its characteristics and benefits. We consider an HFL network organized in a circular area of a 300 m radius. $M = 3$ edge servers are randomly placed at the perimeter of the circular area, and $N = 10$ users are uniformly spatially distributed within the area. The position of the cloud server does not affect the simulation results since the communications established at the backhaul network part are beyond the scope of this paper. The channel gain between any user and its associated edge server is set as $G_{n,m} = \rho d_{n,m}^{-\alpha}$, where $\rho = -20$ dB is the path loss at the reference distance of 1 m, $d_{n,m}$ [m] is the Euclidean distance between user n and edge server m , and $\alpha = 3.5$ is the path loss exponent. The rest of the communication parameters are set as $I_0^m = B_m N_0 = \frac{B}{N} N_0$, with $B = 10$ MHz, $N_0 = -174$ dBm/Hz, $p_{max} = 1$ W, $f_n = 1$ CPU cycles/sec, $a_n = 2 * 10^{-28}$, and $c_n = 20$ CPU cycles/bit, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$ [2]. Regarding the learning process, we consider $K = 100$, $k_1 = 6$, $k_2 = 10$, $\eta = 10^{-3}$, $Z(\mathbf{w}_n) = 28.1$ Kbits, and use the dataset MNIST by randomly selecting 400 samples out of it for each user [2], [13]. Finally, for the satisfaction game algorithm, we assume - unless otherwise explicitly stated - the utility thresholds u_n^{thr} for each user lying within the range $[9, 9.5] * 10^5$ and the convergence limit being equal to 500 iterations. The number of power states $p_{n,m}, \forall n, m$ is 100 (range $[0, p_{max}]$ with step 0.01).

First, we study the performance of the proposed satisfaction game-based framework on the global model produced by the HFL network. For this purpose, the proposed framework is compared against two other approaches that deal with the joint problem of user association and power control in the wireless network differently. In particular, the additional approaches considered are the following: the (i) "Random States" and the

Fig. 1: Convergence behavior and test accuracy of the global HFL model under the proposed framework and the comparative approaches.

(ii) "Satisfaction Game - Energy". According to the former, each user randomly selects one of the available edge servers and its corresponding uplink transmission power level under the condition that this lies within the feasible range $[0, p_{max}]$. In the second approach, the interactions between the users are modeled as a satisfaction game, but, differently from the proposed framework, they aim to satisfy a threshold that solely concerns their personal energy consumption, i.e., the studied utility function is $u_n = \sum_{m=1}^M a_{n,m} \frac{E_{n,m}^{tx}}{E_{n,m}^{tx} + \kappa_1 E_n^{comp}}$. In the latter scenario, the utility threshold u_n^{thr} used for the energy-based satisfaction game is determined manually by closely observing the range of values of the users' energy consumption by the proposed framework to conclude to a feasible and fair comparison.

In Fig. 1, the variation of the global model's accuracy achieved over the test set is presented as a function of the cloud iterations, i.e., epochs, under the proposed and the two comparative approaches. As observed, the proposed framework concludes with a remarkably high value for accuracy (around 95%), thus verifying that the studied technique offers high performance for the learning process. After around 8-10 iterations, the convergence is accomplished, and gradually the accuracy reaches its final value. The proposed framework outperforms the two comparative approaches that do not explicitly consider the performance of the learning process via the uniform distribution of the data to the different edge servers in the HFL network. Specifically, the "Satisfaction Game - Energy" approach achieves the worst results due to the emphasis given to energy reduction, which causes a bad tradeoff for accuracy-energy.

Fig. 2 depicts the total energy consumed by the users (left axis) along with the total entropy achieved in the system (right axis) after the convergence of the proposed and the two comparative approaches. The numerical results show that the proposed framework provides concurrently low energy consumption for the users and the highest global model

Fig. 2: Total users' energy consumption and network's entropy under the proposed framework and the comparative approaches.

accuracy for the HFL method, accomplishing, in this way, the desired accuracy-energy tradeoff. The "Random States" approach fails to control the RAN traffic resulting in increased energy consumption to the users due to interference between them while yielding a fair value in the information entropy of the network, which is attributed to its random nature in distributing data to the different edge servers. On the other hand, the "Satisfaction Game - Energy" approach focusing on the users' energy consumption aspect, sacrifices the entropy of the network and ultimately the overall global model's accuracy, as concluded from Fig. 1.

To further examine the inherent properties of the proposed satisfaction game-based approach, we proceed to analysis over different values of network-related and algorithmic parameters. In more detail, Fig. 3 illustrates the total energy consumed by all the users for communication and computation purposes along with the total entropy achieved in the HFL network, under different values of the utility threshold set by the users in the game in satisfaction form. For the convenience of the comparison and user uniformity purposes, in this experiment, we have assumed that all users have identical requirements for the energy-accuracy tradeoff, i.e., utility threshold u_n^{thr} . From Fig. 3, it is easily observed that as the satisfaction threshold increases and the users' requirements get more strict, the total users' energy decreases, whereas the network's entropy increases. Apparently, the outcome is a user-to-edge-server association and uplink transmission power level selection that distributes more efficiently the data to the different edge servers while maintaining low interference levels for the users.

Continuing, in Fig. 4, we study how the behavior of the network is affected by the number of users participating in the learning process by examining the mean energy of each user and the network's total entropy. The results reveal that the presence of more users results in higher energy consumption by each of them. Indeed, maintaining the number of edge servers fixed leads to a greater aggregation of users with each

Fig. 3: Total users' energy consumption and network's entropy under different satisfaction thresholds.

edge server, increasing the interference caused among them and thus increasing their energy consumption. On the contrary, the higher number of users provokes an increment in the network's entropy and the global model's performance. The additional users joining the HFL network bring a wider variety of samples to the aggregated training dataset \mathcal{D} , allowing for better distribution of the dataset's classes among the different edge servers. It should be noted that the small variations in the values of the entropy are due to the small number of different classes (10-digit classes) included in the studied dataset, which does not give the potential for significant changes in the distribution of the samples.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper, the joint problem of user-to-edge-server association and uplink power allocation in a wireless HFL network was studied to achieve a good tradeoff for users between personal energy consumption and the global model's performance. In particular, the information entropy metric was used as a measure of the global model's performance, i.e., accuracy. The joint problem was formulated as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form, based on which each user, being characterized by different requirements, aimed to maintain the studied tradeoff to such a level that a high-accuracy global model is created without consuming large quantities of energy. The Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE) that satisfies these requirements was examined, and an appropriate RL-based algorithm was used to determine it. The numerical results verified the effectiveness of the proposed framework in achieving the desirable tradeoff of accuracy-energy when compared against other approaches.

Our future work will focus on the examination of different types of satisfaction equilibria that can further target achieving the lowest possible energy consumption on the users' behalf. Accounting for the communications that take place at the backhaul network part is also an extension of our current work.

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Fig. 4: Total users' energy consumption and network's entropy under different numbers of users.

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